

GIVEN THAT KNOWLEDGE OF MATHEMATICS IS ALSO IMPORTANT IN THE WORK OF PSYCHOLOGISTS, MEASURES TO IMPROVE THE MATHEMATICAL SKILLS OF SPECIALISTS IN THE FIELD

Abulqosimov Humoyun

He is a 10th grade student at the Presidential School in Jizzakh

+998970258986

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Training of pedagogical staff of higher pedagogical schools, as well as psychological sciences for all state structures and public organizations on the basis of the strategy, development of the system of continuing education in the country, the rich spiritual heritage and universal values of our people, achievements in culture, economy, science and technology. system and identified key tasks to revitalize the implementation of education reforms. The wide implementation of these issues is the training of competitive personnel who can meet modern requirements. Of course, this requires knowledge of human psychology and an understanding of the psychological changes that take place in them. In this process, we can see the growing need for psychological knowledge. Because in order

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the importance of mathematics in the work of experts in the field, given the growing role of psychologists in any field, and measures to increase their knowledge in the use of mathematical operations in research processes. The article also provides valuable information needed to develop the mathematical skills of industry professionals. Experts in the field who do not have the ability to perform mathematical operations are given information on the further development of mental thinking in relation to mathematical operations, arithmetic, taking into account the importance of mathematical ability in the analysis of psychological tests.

to gain knowledge about people, one must first be aware of psychological knowledge. Serious attention to the formation of the individual on the basis of knowledge of human psychology, ensuring its social development plays an important role in the development of our country. In this process, the National Training Program provides ample opportunities as a unique Uzbek model of continuing education. The focus of this model, founded by the First President of the Republic IA Karimov, is, first of all, the formation of the individual and his activity as a subject of all educational reforms. After all, the result of the implementation of this program is a person with all-round intellectual potential, production skills and socio-political knowledge. The solution of this huge task depends on the human factor, in

which the special role, potential and responsibility of the psychological sciences are clearly felt. Especially after the independence of the republic, the growing attention to the science of psychology has led to the development of work in this area. As long as a person exists, he is based on his life experience, in one way or another perception, comprehension of the universe, separation of things and events is self-explanatory. During the day, we hear birdsong, the sound of musical instruments, human speech, the sound of flying planes, and we see things, trees, animals, and cars all around us. We can distinguish their color and size. These processes are closely related to the nature of reflection in humans. When analyzing the subject of psychology, the main focus should be on: In particular, psychology and pedagogy can be included in the list of disciplines that think about the person. Accordingly, while pedagogy studies the development of the individual in the educational process, psychology studies the mental processes that take place in the individual. From this we can say that the subject of psychology is the psyche of the individual and his psychological characteristics.

The word psychology is derived from the Greek psyuxe - soul, spirit, logos - science means doctrine. Psychological facts as a science of psychology, learns their laws and mechanisms. Psychology is basically the study of the psyche in a wide range. Accordingly, the basic mental activities of the psyche are shown.

Specific mental activities include:

- Cognitive activities: attention, speech, activity;

- Cognitive processes: intuition, perception, memory, imagination, thinking;
- Personal, emotional, volitional sphere: - emotion, will;
- Individual psychological characteristics of the person: temperament, character, ability.

Different methods are effectively used today in the detection of mental activities, situations. One of the most commonly used methods is the test method. Questionnaires and observation methods are also widely used. These techniques can be used to study individuals as well as large and small groups. The test method can usually be convenient for getting information from the public, but it is not possible to get complete information. In general, as a result of conducting methods in groups by experts in the field, it is possible to identify different mental states, to show people the right direction to find their solutions. At the same time, psychologists need mathematical knowledge and skills to produce test results. For example, math ability is important in the Risk Test, the Adolescent Character Accentuation Test, the Nervous System Characteristics Test, and other tests. Because the answers have to be calculated correctly. It is also important to know the rules of division, multiplication, addition and subtraction. It is also important to know the operations between negative and positive numbers. You need to know when the answers to math problems are negative and when the answers are positive. For example, if a person does not know mathematics well, he may say that a large number cannot be divided by a small number. However, such actions are correct and in this case the result will be negative. Specialists can often encounter such actions in the process of

calculating the results of psychological tests, and they also need to be well versed in mathematical operations in order to calculate the results correctly and make an accurate diagnosis. Mathematical operations are used in the study of population psychology to obtain accurate and precise results, as well as to determine statistics. So psychologists need to know how to calculate percentages. It is also important to know the fractions in order to calculate the shares. It can be said that it is better to know short calculation operations and formulas, so that it does not take much time to analyze many tests. Only in order for the results to be accurate are the experts in the field required to improve their mathematical skills and constantly work on themselves. It is no secret that in recent years, as a result of the development of the IT industry, the digital economy, mathematics has entered every field, and this science is becoming an integral part of

any field. Knowing it is now a requirement of the times in any field. The purpose of talking about the place and role of mathematics in psychology is that it is now important in almost every aspect of our lives. By helping one person manage his or her life, these professionals can, in time, disrupt or disrupt the life of any group or community as a whole. So how the people, the people in the society, can find their way in the future will also depend in some way on how psychologists approach their tasks. Of course, the professionalism of psychologists plays a big role in this. Professional skills, on the other hand, need to be constantly updated with knowledge and hard work. I think one of the requirements of this field is to develop the ability to do logical and mathematical operations. After all, accurate and precise knowledge is needed to get accurate and precise results from psychological research conducted in humans today.

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